

Technodiversity, performance, and technical mediation in four creative projects exploring interactive and visual resources

José Henrique Padovani*

ORCID: 0000-0002-8919-7393

Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais
Belo Horizonte, Minas Gerais, Brasil
jhp@ufmg.br

Caio Costa Campos

ORCID: 0000-0002-6702-7799

Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais
Belo Horizonte, Minas Gerais, Brasil
costacaio campos@gmail.com

Abstract

In this paper we explore the relationship between technology, performance, and creative invention drawing on concepts of *cosmotronics/technodiversity* and theories of performance and technical mediation. By opposing the hegemonic, universalizing view of technology/culture and the conceptualization of performance as an entanglement of technical systems and embodied actions, we discuss aspects of four artistic projects that integrate interactive and audiovisual elements. In conclusion, the paper asserts the importance for artists, particularly those in contexts considered peripheral, to resist the homogenizing force of a dominant “monotechnology”. It advocates for a critical and creative appropriation of technology that fosters situated and contextualized artistic invention.

Keywords

Technodiversity, Cosmotronics, Performance, Creative Processes, Technology Appropriation

1 Introduction

Technical mediation and *performance* are central aspects of artistic practices that engage with interactive means: they address the relations between humans, technical systems, and performative actions within creative processes. Nevertheless, these aspects are often taken for granted, potentially masking the cultural, social, and idiosyncratic dimensions inherent in any artistic and technical practice within a given context.

The present paper explores the interrelations between technology, mediation, invention, and performance within the creative processes of four interactive audiovisual works. This exploration is framed by Yuk Hui’s concepts of *cosmotronics* and *technodiversity* [12–17], which are articulated with a conceptualization of *performance* as a framework for understanding the entanglement of technical systems, expressive intentions, and embodied actions in creative works [22]. Following the introduction of these theoretical concepts, we address the technical and performative aspects of the four projects, each exploring interactive and audiovisual resources through personal appropriations of technology. These works are discussed by tracing the connections between their technical creation, expressive intentions, and performance dimensions. The pieces are divided into two groups: (1) two compositions involving the development of computer vision algorithms that retrieve and provide feedback on physical information from the musicians’ performances; (2) two pieces in which the video capture of the

performances—their mediatization—is explored as compositional material.

In the following section, Yuk Hui’s concepts of *cosmotronics* and *technodiversity* are introduced, highlighting their relationship to art and contrasting them with a hegemonic, monolithic notion of *technology*. These concepts are articulated with a conceptualization of *performance* in section three. By situating the works discussed in this text within this theoretical framework, this paper discusses the visions of *technology* in *performance* and explores their potential connections with Hui’s concepts.

Sections four and five discuss some aspects of the four pieces taking into account the preceding theoretical framework. We first examine the diversity of techniques, software, and tools (technical objects) adapted, crafted, and explored in the creative and performative processes of each work. Then, we relate the performative, poetic, and expressive intentions of the pieces to the technical and research dimensions of their creative process.

The conclusion argues that, particularly for artists-researchers dealing with new technologies in contexts considered peripheral, it is crucial to resist the homogenizing force of hegemonic monoculture/monotechnology.

2 *Cosmotronics* and *technodiversity*

There is a general misconception that all technics are equal, that all skills and artificial products coming from all cultures can be reduced to one thing called ‘technology’. And indeed, it is almost impossible to deny that technics can be understood as the extension of the body or the exteriorisation of memory. Yet they may not be *perceived* or reflected upon in the same way in different cultures. [16, p. 9]

In *The Question Concerning Technology in China: An Essay in Cosmotronics*, Yuk Hui challenges the universalist conception of technology. He posits that our understanding of *technology* and *technics*, as philosophical concepts tied to the human activity of making and practice, cannot be assumed to be universal. Instead, Hui argues it is fundamentally shaped by the history of philosophy and, more importantly, by the specific cosmology of the culture in which it emerges: “in China, technics in the sense we understand it today — or at least as it is defined by certain European philosophers — never existed” [16, p. 9].

To highlight this distinction, Hui introduces the concept of *cosmotronics*:

I propose to go beyond the notion of cosmology; instead, it would be more productive to

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address what I call cosmotechnics. Let me give you a preliminary definition of cosmotechnics: it is the unification of the cosmos and the moral through technical activities, whether craft-making or art-making. [11, p. 6].

Hui traces the hegemonic modern cosmotechnics to its Greek origins and its evolution into what contemporary anthropologists like Philippe Descola and Eduardo Viveiros de Castro call *naturalism* — a worldview that segregates nature and culture [8]. Although the seeds of this division are present in Greek thought through binaries such as man/gods, invisible/visible, and eternal/mortal, Hui argues that the definitive separation occurred during the modern period.

Through the concept of *cosmotechnics*, Hui critiques the multifaceted nature of this *homogenization*. While Viveiros de Castro and Descola respond to this problem with *multinaturalism* — a concept that itself requires questioning the *nature/culture* dichotomy — Hui’s approach goes down another path. He argues that the nature/culture dichotomy is itself a symptom of a deeper issue: the universalization of a single, modern concept of technology. His critique therefore focuses not on ontology directly, but on technics as the mediating activity between a cosmos and a culture. Influenced by Bernard Stiegler, he seeks to dismantle the *nature/technology* divide, while also, echoing the foundational influence of Gilbert Simondon, challenging the separation between *technique* and *culture*. [6, 24, 29]

Against this homogenization — which we identify also, in a Gramscian sense, as a process of *hegemonization* — Hui connects the concept of *technodiversity* with those of *biodiversity* and *noodiversity* (the diversity of knowledge).

In reality, what Vandana Shiva called the “monoculture of the mind” is omnipresent in the capitalist logic of globalization; we, therefore, end up having monotecnology, which recklessly views itself as the only option. The “monoculture of the mind”, which endangers both biodiversity and noodiversity, suggests that the key to resolving this problem is to return to the discourse of technodiversity. Therefore, the matrix of biodiversity, noodiversity, and technodiversity form a more comprehensive framework than the dialectics between nature and technology for understanding the planetary condition. The question of bifurcation is central since, without differentiation and diversification, it is impossible to talk about difference and diversity. Diversity is not only to be maintained, but it also has to be *constantly created*. [17, p. 225-226]

The hegemonic cosmotechnics of our time, the “monoculture of the mind,” is not merely an ideology of the homogenization of cultural practices and values, landscapes, social life, knowledge, and worldviews. It also hinders the diversity of ways of thinking and making. In the context of art, it restricts the plurality of the creative and aesthetic appropriation, reinvention, and exploration of technology, as well as technology’s position in the world.

This is why Hui points out that it is not sufficient to maintain the plurality of cultural, technical, and natural idiosyncrasies. Indeed, there is always the risk of “diversity,” “preservation,” and “conservation” being articulated as *conservative* euphemisms for the status quo by isolating, hoarding, and exhibiting its trophies, both captured and designated: like ‘exotic’ plants in a botanical garden, or taxidermized animals and dioramas in a ‘natural history’ museum. Walter Benjamin already pointed out that these spoils, the so-called *cultural goods* [Kulturgüter], are at the same time a monument of culture and a monument of barbarism [1]. This ever-relevant lesson applies not only to the looted cultural goods exhibited in museums such as the Pergamonmuseum in Berlin, the British Museum in London, the Louvre in Paris, or the AfricaMuseum in Brussels, but also to a broader set of institutionalized practices towards nature and technology that are based on the same logic of *conservation* and *preservation*, on one side, and *innovation* and *technical progress*, on the other (two other terms that are often used as perverse euphemisms for *homogenization-hegemonization*).

Diversities and *pluralities* are to be constantly created in their living and situated relations with the world, within their multiple cultural, technical, and natural milieus. For biological, cultural, and technical differences — and *différences*, as this multiplicity is also related to temporalities [7] — have their own dynamics and contextualized *individuation* processes. The political position of taking the “matrix of biodiversity, noodiversity, and technodiversity” as an ethical standpoint is, we believe, to sustain and foster the conditions for the dynamic processes of the *individuation of diversities* [25–27].

This perspective must face contradictions inherent to the artistic practices and experiences of our time, including the *homogenization-hegemonization* of aesthetic experiences.

To insist on the varieties of experience of art is not simply to identify the different aesthetic experiences that have become obvious today, but rather to penetrate into their variant forms of aesthetic thinking [...] This question, of course, applies to art, but also to thinking in its totality. The process of modernization qua technological globalization seems to have obliterated these differences. Like in Rem Koolhaas’s generic city, a universal aesthetics arises out of the postmodern celebration of cultural rootlessness. [15, p. 27]

3 Performance and technical mediation

The question of *technodiversity* — and, in a more general sense, of *diversities* as discussed in the last section — intersects with the questions of *performance* and *technical mediation*.

Performance thought, articulated through the so-called performative turn of anthropology, may be a useful framework towards these diversities. At the same time, it might be related to similar celebrations of rootlessness and universality, while not in their most obvious and direct form.

Despite the numerous conceptions of performance, a certain unity exists among them. Conquergood identifies at its roots a *shift from mimesis to kinesis*, viewing culture as an active verb rather than a noun [5]. We can also consider a more general comprehension

of “humans, things and matter as not being fixed but in a process of changing and becoming” [22, p. xxx]. Or, more concretely in relation to art, as something that defies precise or easy definition beyond the simple declaration that it is “live art by artists” [9, p. 9].

While these notions do not account for the perception of hegemonic *cosmotronics* or its effects on performance theory itself, both Hui’s notion of *cosmotronics* and the performative turn share a critique of static, object-centered views of culture, art, and technology¹. Just as technics and technology exist only in relation to a specific cosmos, approaching art as performance can highlight the relationship between a performance’s technics and its *milieu*.

A comprehensive definition of performance is a task that extends beyond the scope of this text². Here, we adopt the definition articulated by Salter in *Entangled: Technology and the Transformation of Performance*: “the performing arts are really an unstable mixture amalgamating light, space, sound, image, bodies, architecture, materials, machines, code, and a perceiving public into unique spatiotemporal events” [22, p. xxii].

Acknowledging that performance resists strict definition, Salter also articulates its diversity of practices through seven characteristics that distinguish it from other artistic perspectives: (1) an interest in *enaction* or doing; (2) real-time, dynamic processes over static objects or representations; (3) engagement with the temporal moment of the present; (4) embodiment and materiality; (5) immanent experience; (6) the effect of both human and nonhuman presence; and (7) transmutation and reconstitution [22, p. xxiii].

Regarding the relationship between technology and performance, he first states that just as technologies are integral to the history of performance, performance is integral to the history of technologies. He then articulates the main questions of his book:

It makes sense that we can put the artifice of technology on the stage to show the workings of the world and that humans can *act out* or *present* something in front of a spectator surrounded by that technology, but how can machines and substance, materials, and spaces perform, especially when they have no consciousness or intention? Why should we grant the human right of performance to inanimate things, especially ones that we have created? How can we confuse artistic performances with the performances of machines, not only in terms of their function or efficiency, but also through the attribution to them of embodied expression? [22, p. xxiii]

The questions raised by Salter point towards a deeper inquiry into the nature of performance and the human-machine dichotomy. Technical objects, since the advent of automata, have been perceived as having a certain degree of agency, even if not conscious or intentional. Furthermore, the divide between human, nonhuman,

and technological beings has been blurred in contemporary artistic practices, where semiautonomous instruments/systems, prosthetically enhanced performers, mechanized human bodies, and synthetically/virtualized performers are increasingly common in diverse performance contexts.

These different *modes of existence* of technology and technics in performance, as well as the different relations between humans and nonhumans, contest pragmatic and utilitarian views of technology. They challenge traditional philosophical definitions of technology that see technical tools as “something to” [um zu], as neutral objects whose ready-to-handness [Zuhandenheit] would make them transparent to the human subject, who notices them only when their usefulness comes to be disturbed by a malfunction or breakdown [10, p. 66-70].

Technologies are not simply inert or neutral artifacts that are, as Heidegger termed it, *ready to hand*: waiting for human presence to activate them and thus extend human action into the world, revealing and framing it in a particular manner. Instead, technologies are similar to Guattari’s machine, constructing and ordering social-cultural-political relations. Technology does something in and to the world by modifying existing relations and constructing new ones between humans, tools, processes and the environment in which all are deeply entangled. [...] More to the point, the question I ask is how technology has mediated and scrambled meanings and categories among artists, events, and spectators, and in what specific contexts it has done these things. [22, p. xxxv]

Salter’s perspective, here, relates to the discussion of *technical mediation* by Bruno Latour, who describes techniques not as mere *means*, “but mediators, means and ends at the same time” [19, p. 197]. Defying the widespread Heideggerian notion of technology, Latour, following a similar line of thought to Descola, Viveiros de Castro, and Tim Ingold, also disputes a central dichotomy in modern thought: the one between *humans* and *nonhumans* (in the sense, here, of technical beings). Technical action is a form of delegation that allows us to mobilize, during interactions, moves made elsewhere, earlier, by other actants” [18, p. 52] — an idea that strongly resonates with Simondon’s notion of the *isodynamism* between the working mechanisms of machines and the dynamism of human thought:

A relation of iso-dynamism exists between man who invents and the machine that functions [...]. The true analogical relation is in fact between the mental functioning of man and the physical functioning of the machine. [...] To invent is to make one’s thought function as a machine might function [...] according to the dynamism of lived functioning, grasped because it is produced, accompanied in its genesis. The machine is a being that functions. Its mechanisms concretize a coherent dynamism that once existed in thought, which were that thought. During

¹According to performance studies, anything can be studied ‘as’ performance. That means asking performance questions of whatever is being studied. What happens? Where does it happen? How does it look, how does it behave, how does it change over time? What effects does the event or thing have on participants and observers?” [23, p. 12].

²For a more detailed discussion of this definition, see Carlson’s *Performance: a critical introduction* [4].

invention, the dynamism of thought converted itself into functioning forms. Inversely, the machine, in functioning, is subject to or produces a certain number of variations around the fundamental rhythms of its functioning, arising from its definite forms. [28, p. 11]

As Salter states, technology is integral to performance exactly because of this differed *mobilization*. Or, as Latour concludes in a more provocative way, because technical artifacts not only mediate our actions:

...if our challenge is to be met, it will not be met by considering artifacts as things. They deserve better. They deserve to be housed in our intellectual culture as full-fledged social actors. They mediate our actions? No, they are us. [18, p. 64]

4 Technical processes explored in four creative projects

In this section, we briefly present some aspects of four creative projects by the authors, highlighting the technical processes involved in their creation and performance: *aēr* (2024-...) and *afterlives* (2020), by José Henrique Padovani; and *facePiece* (2025) and *Toca* (2024-25), by Caio Costa Campos. Since each pair of pieces we have composed shares similar technical processes, we will discuss them side-by-side.

While the previous sections focused on *technodiversity* and *performance* from a critical-theoretical perspective, here we will concentrate on the practical technical-creative aspects that concretely engage with these concepts in our creation-research processes.

4.1 *aēr* and *Toca*: computer vision and real-time visuals

aēr (2024-...) and *Toca* (2024-25) are pieces that use interaction processes based on computer vision and real-time visuals to explore mediation and performance³.

aēr is an ongoing creative project for bandoneon and a distributed interactive audiovisual system where separate computers handle the audio and visuals. The piece is performed by a bandoneonist whose movements are captured by a depth camera and processed by custom-built computer vision processes designed to track the instrument's varying features, such as its shape, inclination, and bellows compression. The visuals are projected onto a large screen behind the performer. The audiovisual setup includes two microphones, an interactive music system in Pure Data that also sends control data to the visuals, and a spatial audio system that spatializes the sound using *ambisonics*.

Two custom processes were developed for the piece: a computer vision process to track the bandoneon and a real-time control system for the game engine using network messages in the *Open Sound Control* (OSC) format.

For the computer vision processes, a Python script and a depth camera are used to capture the plane of the bandoneon bellows

and the performer's hands. As the performer's legs are in this same plane, a predefined mask is applied to filter out irrelevant areas, yielding an image where only the instrument and hands are visible as a moving white blob. This image is blurred and thresholded to generate a clean binary (black and white) version that highlights the target shapes with less detail and noise. The subsequent processes are based on detecting features from the resulting white blob, particularly the shape, centroid, inclination, extrema, and compression of the bandoneon bellows (Figure 1). The extraction of these features follows a pipeline that begins by identifying the largest white area and simplifying its contour into a more manageable polygon. From this polygon, the system calculates the centroid to track the instrument's overall position, while a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) determines the main axis of the shape, which is used to infer the bandoneon's overall inclination. To analyze the bellows' state, the system identifies the two extreme points where this principal axis intersects the polygon. The line between these extremes is then virtually sliced by a series of perpendicular lines, dividing the main polygon into smaller segments. By analyzing the centroids and areas of these individual slices, the system derives advanced metrics, including the bellows' degree of compression and its curvature, which is quantified as a bend factor. Finally, all extracted parameters are continuously smoothed, normalized to a standard range, and transmitted in real-time to the game engine using OSC network messages, providing data to drive the interactive visuals and real-time audio processes.

Figure 1: Computer vision processes explored in *aēr*

The visuals are programmed in the open-source game engine UPBGE, based on the open-source 3D suite Blender. As the game engine is not designed for *Open Sound Control* (OSC) messages, another custom Python script was developed to receive the OSC messages and convert them into the game engine's internal logic. This script allows, for example, the bandoneon's movement to change the properties of virtual objects in the game engine: for

³A video-performance of *Toca* (2024) can be found here. Its documentation, such as score and code, can also be found at eucaio.art

Figure 2: Visuals and computer vision interaction tests for *aēr*. Performer: Francisco Cesar.

instance, the bellows' compression and expansion can control the gravity of a scene, while the centroid position can control an invisible object that displaces leaves, creating wind-like effects (Figure 2).

Toca is a piece for guitar, hands, and interactive projection. It is performed in a blackout, employing an interactive system developed in Python and Processing that tracks and projects spotlights onto the performer's hands and parts of the guitar. At times, the spotlights follow the performer's hands or specific guitar parts. At other times, they illuminate parts of the instrument not being directly activated by the hands (Figure 3). This process creates assemblages of the performer's body, the instrument, their movements, the sounds produced, and their relations during the performance, which the piece explores as its primary material.

Figure 3: *Toca* frames, took from different moments of the piece

As in *aēr*, a depth camera is used in *Toca*. Instead of tracking the instrument's shape through custom set of instrument shape features, *Toca* focuses on tracking the performer's hands and parts of the guitar, particularly the soundhole. The strategy involves identifying blobs in the depth image that are closer to the camera,

Figure 4: Computer vision processes explored in *Toca*

as the performer positions their hands in front of the guitar during the performance. A similar strategy is employed to detect parts of the guitar, especially the soundhole (Figure 4).

This tracking data forms the basis for the projections, which are manipulated in real-time by a second performer using a MIDI controller. Following the score, this performer adjusts the size and position of the projected spotlights for two main purposes: first, to fine-tune the tracking and ensure the projections align correctly on stage; and second, to creatively alter the spotlight positions, occasionally illuminating parts of the guitar not being directly played, as specified in the score.

4.2 *facePiece* and *afterlives*: Tiling, Face Choreography, and Media-Specificity

facePiece (2025) is a piece for faces⁴. Fifteen performers were recorded individually, with a camera focusing on their faces as they followed a tablature detailing precise facial muscle movements and specific timing. All performers executed the same score, and their recordings are later synchronized and projected side-by-side with no sound (Figures 5 and 6). The projections feature the faces at the largest possible scale, constituting the work's presence as an installation.

The recordings were also compiled into a single video, with each face positioned in a grid. This alternative *montage* shapes the relationships between the faces differently, highlighting a key characteristic of the piece: its malleable articulation across multiple

⁴A video-performance of *facePiece* (2025) can be found here. Its score and other versions, such as documentation of its installation, can also be found at eucaio.art

Figure 5: *facePiece* frame, in its single video version for circulation online. Performers are doing their first open faces

Figure 6: Fourth system of *facePiece*'s score, indicating which facial muscles should be activated at each moment. The score is accompanied by a video-score also indicating the timing of each movement with a click track.

contexts. This diversifies the potential relationships between the faces, the recording media, and the contexts in which it is presented.

afterlives (2020) is a piece for flute and an interactive audiovisual system, originally conceived for performance on a streaming platform, as it premiered during the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic [20]. In the original version, a flutist performs facing a webcam, and his image is displayed across 25 tiles on a screen resembling a video-call interface. The flutist's image and audio are captured and processed in real-time using continuously changing delay processes. These processes allow the performer's present image and sounds to be mixed with his past, transformed movements and sounds.

The video processing is achieved using a video buffer that stores frames captured by the camera. Each of the 25 tiles is programmed to continuously change its buffer position and brightness. Likewise, the audio is processed via phase vocoder and granular synthesis

Figure 7: *afterlives* frame. Version for streaming platform performed by Gabriel Rimoldi.

techniques, which allow the live sound to be transformed in real-time by shifting it back and forth in time and altering its pitch and timbre.

The piece has also been adapted for the stage. In this version, the tiled screen is replaced by five distinct projection surfaces arranged on stage, onto which the performer's full-body image is projected in real scale. While the fundamental audiovisual processing system is unchanged, this adaptation incorporates video mapping techniques to precisely align the projections with the physical surfaces⁵.

5 Technical mediation, performance, and technodiversity in the pieces

Art is closely related to technology, and looking at technology from the perspective of art may be able to reveal something extraordinary. [15, p. 28]

The creative projects presented in the previous section are the practical and technical manifestations of the theoretical discussion in the earlier sections. As is often the case in research-creation processes and practice-based research methodologies, such aspects involve processes of technical and artistic imagination characterized by the need to create particular technical *artefacts* and strategies to enable the expressive intentions of each piece [2, 3]. Conversely, these technical mediation processes also inform and inspire new creative ideas.

Yet, such technical solutions and expressive intentions maintain a certain independence. While the first two pieces (*aēr* and *Toca*) share a similar approach in terms of resources and technical mediation strategies, mainly demanding the development of similar computer vision interaction processes, the expressive ideas that guide them are quite distinct: while *aēr* seeks to emphasize and make perceptible (in images and sounds) the malleable, sonorous, and airy qualities of the instrument and its manipulation by the performer, *Toca* explores the assemblages between the performer's body and the parts of the guitar in their articulations with its tradition of performance and idiomaticism.

⁵The "live" (stage) version of *afterlives* was not yet premiered.

In the creative process of *aër*, this oneiric image of an instrument that bends and manipulates air guided the gradual and incremental process of experimentation, creation, and appropriation of algorithms and technical strategies. This involved researching depth cameras (Kinect versions 1 and 2, Arducam ToF Depth Camera), spatial plane segmentation techniques, developing techniques to extract visual features from the bandoneon’s shape, and developing strategies to control the UPBGE game development environment via OSC commands.

On the other hand, *Toca* explores the poetic idea of composing a performance in which light projections onto the performer’s hands and parts of the guitar guide the audience’s perception in an automated and hyper-focused manner. In this case, the development of the computer vision processes was aimed to track these elements, enabling to project spotlights above them. While the tracking system articulates this automation, the presence of a second performer, who controls the size and position of the projected spots, diversifies the possible relationships between the generated assemblages.

In contrast, *facePiece* and *afterlives* explore different technical mediation strategies to achieve similar expressive intentions.

facePiece explores the time-deferred recording of each face following a precise temporality, prescribed in a tablature-like score, and synchronized in the installation’s projection. *afterlives*, in turn, requires a fluid logic of real-time audiovisual processing, making use of video buffers, phase vocoders, and sound granulation processes.

While the technical mediation strategies are distinct, it is possible to say that both pieces have a similar “physiognomy”: the performers’ faces in *facePiece* and the flutist images in *afterlives* build textural relationships. Although the resources to achieve this are distinct, the continuous delay lines or the score prescription of facial movements allow for the creation of dynamic conductions and articulations based on the similarity and difference between the projected faces. This visual choreography not only articulates the media moment by moment but also reverberates in a formal/temporal dimension of the performances.

6 Conclusion and future work

The dissemination of technological objects and their use in different areas and contexts today is marked by the logic of capitalism and consumer society. In this context, *monotechnology* and *monoculture* tend to create a homogenization and a fetishization of technology, limiting its artistic and expressive potential. This tendency, in the field of art, points to a creatively sterile horizon in which the diversity and plurality of modes of imagination and artistic expressions are suffocated by a hegemonic, positivist, and one-dimensional view of artistic creation.

The ideas and practices related to the concepts of *cosmotronics* and *technodiversity* allow us to think about these issues on a broader horizon and help overcome dualisms related to *culture* and *technology*, pointing to particular strategies of technological appropriation. Similarly, the rethinking of *performance* and *technical mediation* allows for a more active reworking of the relationship between technology and art and, at the same time, highlights that every creative project takes place in a situated and specific context. Especially in places regarded as peripheral in relation to the centers

of technological development, these contexts demand their own technical and artistic articulations that, instead of merely following the latest trends and fashions from elsewhere, foster relational, situated, and diverse processes of techno-artistic invention [21].

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